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**A STUDY OF THE ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE OF COLLEGES OF EDUCATION
IN RELATION TO THE ATTITUDE OF TEACHER-EDUCATORS TOWARDS
TEACHING PROFESSION**

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Abstract:

Effective and productive learning can be achieved only by teachers with desirable attitudes. Teachers' job performance is the way in which a teacher behaves in the process of teaching and it is known to be related to teachers' effectiveness. It is said that good performance of students depends upon effective teaching of their teachers. Thus, it is important to examine the factor that could enhance teachers' job performance. The main purpose of this study was to examine the influence of organizational climate on Teachers' Attitude towards Teaching Profession. The Organizational Climate of any work place plays a very important role in various aspects of its employees i.e. their performance, attitude and the quality of product they produce. Teachers' belief, views and their attitudes affect their teaching and behaviour with the students. The teachers thinking , their job satisfaction and their expectation from the job all such things affect their work. We know that the future of the students is in the hand of the teachers. Then we must know about the teachers who impart education and mould our future generation. So here the investigator tried to know attitude of the teacher-educators towards teaching profession. The quality of education depends on many factors. The present study attempted to study such two factors i.e. Organizational Climate of colleges of education and the Attitude of Teacher-Educators towards Teaching Profession. It was found that if the Organizational Climate is favourable, teacher educators attribute higher attitude towards teaching profession.

Key Word:

Organizational climate, Attitude of Teacher-Educators towards Teaching Profession

INTRODUCTION:

Organizational climate can be defined as an approach in which organizational members observe and characterize their surrounding and environment in an attitudinal and value-based manner. Effective performance of any work requires the right attitude toward the work. As pointed out by Ahluwalia S.P. (1978), “A positive favourable attitude makes the work not only easier but also more satisfying and professionally rewarding. A negative unfavourable attitude makes the teaching task hard, more tedious and unpleasant.” Attitudes are not inborn or innate. They are not inherited by the individual but are acquired by her/him during the growth process. The Organizational Climate of any work place plays a very important role in various aspects of its employees i.e. their performance, attitude and the quality of product they produce. The quality of education depends on many factors. The present study attempted to study such one factor i.e. Organizational Climate of colleges of education. Climate of the organization is affected by almost everything that occurs in the organization making it a dynamic system concept. The daily relationships and interactions of employees are indicative of an organizational climate.

From the review of studies conducted in India & Abroad, the researcher can conclude that the overall Organizational Climate varies from institute to institute. In some studies, it was found that teachers were more satisfied in open organizational climate. Gender and teaching experience of teachers does not show significant difference in terms of Organizational Climate. The review has enabled the investigator to develop the present research study which will contribute to the fund of existing knowledge in the field of Organizational Climate

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the Organizational Climate of colleges of Education on the basis of -
 - a. Gender
 - b. Region
 - c. Type of college
 - d. Age
 - e. Teaching experience
2. To compare the Organizational Climate of colleges of Education on the basis of -
 - a. Gender
 - b. Region
 - c. Type of college
 - d. Age
 - e. Teaching experience

3. To study the attitude of Teacher-Educators towards teaching profession on the basis of –

- a. Gender
- b. Region
- c. Type of college
- d. Age
- e. Teaching experience

4. To compare the attitude of Teacher-Educators towards teaching profession on the basis of

- a. Gender
- b. Region
- c. Type of college
- d. Age
- e. Teaching experience

5. To ascertain the correlation between Organizational Climate of colleges of Education and attitude of Teacher-Educators towards teaching profession on the basis of -

- a. Gender
- b. Region
- c. Type of college
- d. Age
- e. Teaching experience

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

To achieve the objectives of the study the following null hypotheses had been formulated:

1. There is no significant difference in the Organizational Climate of colleges of Education on the basis of -

- a. Gender
- b. Region
- c. Type of college
- d. Age
- e. Teaching experience

2. There is no significant difference in the Attitude of Teacher-Educators towards teaching profession on the basis of –

- a. Gender
- b. Region
- c. Type of college
- d. Age
- e. Teaching experience

3. There is no significant correlation between Organizational Climate of colleges of Education and Attitude of Teacher-Educators towards teaching profession on the basis of-
- Gender
 - Region
 - Type of college
 - Age
 - Teaching experience

Design of the Study

In the present study, the researcher attempted to study the Organizational Climate of Colleges of Education in relation to the Attitude of teacher-educators towards the teaching profession. The method adopted here is the descriptive method. All the Teacher educators of Government, Aided and Unaided Colleges of Education affiliated to University of Mumbai constitute the population of interest. , the sample consisted of 302 Teacher-Educators of Govt., Aided & Unaided colleges of education affiliated to the University of Mumbai. There were total 76 colleges of education affiliated to the University of Mumbai at the time of study. Out of which 3 colleges are run by the Govt., 7 are Aided & 66 are Unaided colleges of education. The colleges of six districts of Maharashtra i.e. Mumbai City, Mumbai Suburban, Thane, Raigad, Ratnagiri and Sindhudurg come under the jurisdiction of University of Mumbai. Hence all these six districts were covered under the study.

For this purpose 100% colleges of education affiliated to University of Mumbai were selected but the selection of teacher-educators from various colleges of education was done by using random sampling techniques.

Table 1-Number of Teacher Educators

Group	Sub-Group	N
Gender	Male	84
	Female	218
Region	Urban	230
	Rural	72

College Type	Government	17
	Aided	66
	Unaided	219
Age	Upto 40 Yrs	200
	Above 40 Yrs	102
Experience	Upto 10 Yrs	219
	Above 10 Yrs	83
Total No. of Teacher educators		302

Table 1 shows the number of Teacher-Educators of Govt., Aided & Unaided colleges of education affiliated to the University of Mumbai included in the sample.

Tools of Research:

Organizational Climate Inventory which was prepared by Somnath Chattopadhyaya & K.G.Agarwal was modified to suit the Organizational Climate of colleges of education. The original inventory had 70 items, each with 5 different alternative answers. For each item alternatives were different. The researcher converted the scale into 5 point scale. This inventory prepared has 50 items which measured the organizational climate taking into consideration the 10 dimensions. The tool was used after affirming its validity and reliability.

Attitude Scale towards teaching profession was used which has been prepared by Dr. Mrs. Umme Kulsum which is a standardized scale. This scale has 55 items covering 5 dimensions. This scale was used as it was. The positive and negative items were arranged randomly. The tools were translated into Marathi language also to get the valid responses from varied respondents. The tools were used after affirming their validity and reliability.

Analysis Of Data

Descriptive and Inferential Analysis of data was done.

For Descriptive Analysis the data was analysed by computing the mean and standard deviation. For Inferential Analysis the data was analysed using appropriate statistical techniques. The following techniques of Data Analysis were used for the study.

1. t-test
2. F-test

3. Pearson's r

Major Findings And Conclusions

Testing Of Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference in the Organizational Climate of colleges of Education on the basis of -

- a. Gender
- b. Region
- c. Type of college
- d. Age
- e. Teaching experience

This null hypothesis is tested for differences in scores of O.C. on the basis of different groups. The results obtained is tabulated in table 1

Table 2

Organizational Climate of colleges of Education on the basis of different groups

Total N=302

Group	Sub-Group	N	Mean	S.D.	t/ F ratio ANOVA	Significance at 0.05 level	Null Hypothesis
Gender	Male	84	185.79	34.24	t= 0.96	N.S.	Accepted
	Female	218	185.58	30.34			
Region	Urban	230	185.47	31.65	t=0.87	N.S.	Accepted
	Rural	72	186.17	30.89			
College Type	Government	17	183.18	32.09	F=3.101	Significant	Rejected
	Aided	66	194.09	29.68			
	Unaided	219	183.28	31.57			
Age	Upto 40 Yrs	200	185.48	30.59	t= 0.95	N.S.	Accepted
	Above 40 Yrs	102	185.70	32.86			
Experienc e	Upto 10 Yrs	219	185.15	29.07	t= 0.66	N.S.	Accepted
	Above 10 Yrs	83	186.92	37.07			

Interpretation:-

The above table shows that the null hypothesis is accepted on the basis of Gender, Region Age & Teaching experience but rejected on the basis of Type of college.

Conclusion:-

There is no significant difference in the Organizational Climate of colleges of Education on the basis of Gender, Region, Age & Teaching experience but it makes difference on the basis of Type of college.

TESTING OF HYPOTHESIS 2

The null hypothesis states that- There is no significant difference in the Attitude of Teacher-Educators towards teaching profession on the basis of –

- a. Gender
- b. Region
- c. Type of college
- d. Age
- e. Teaching experience

This hypothesis is tested for differences in scores of Attitude of Teacher-Educators towards teaching profession on the basis of different groups The result obtained is tabulated in table 3

Table 3

Attitude of Teacher-Educators towards Teaching Profession on the basis of different groups

Group	Sub-Group	N	Mean	S.D.	t/ F ratio ANOVA	Significance at 0.05 level	Null Hypothesis
Gender	Male	84	169.68	18.91	t= 0.78	N.S.	Accepted
	Female	218	169.03	18.23			
Region	Urban	230	169.13	17.73	t= 0.93	N.S.	Accepted
	Rural	72	169.44	20.49			
College Type	Government	17	173.35	15.93	F=7.164	Significant	Rejected
	Aided	66	176.08	15.84			
	Unaided	219	166.82	18.77			

Age	Upto 40 Yrs	200	168.30	18.56	t= 0.22	N.S.	Accepted
	Above 40 Yrs	102	171.03	17.84			
Experienc e	Upto 10 Yrs	219	168.16	18.71	t= 0.11	N.S.	Accepted
	Above 10 Yrs	83	171.98	17.35			

Interpretation:-

The above table shows that the null hypothesis is accepted on the basis of Gender, Region Age & Teaching experience but rejected on the basis of Type of college.

Conclusion:-

There is no significant difference in the Attitude of Teacher-Educators towards teaching profession on the basis of Gender, Region, Age & Teaching experience but it makes difference on the basis of Type of college.

TESTING OF HYPOTHESIS 3

The null hypothesis states that- There is no significant correlation between Organizational Climate of colleges of Education and Attitude of Teacher-Educators towards teaching profession on the basis of -

- a. Gender
- b. Region
- c. Type of college
- d. Age
- e. Teaching experience

This hypothesis is tested for correlation between Organizational Climate of colleges of Education and Attitude of Teacher-Educators towards teaching profession. The result obtained is tabulated in table 4

Table -4

Correlation between Organizational Climate of colleges of Education and Attitude of Teacher-Educators towards teaching profession

Group	Sub-Group	r	Significance at 0.05 Level	Correlation	Null Hypothesis
Gender	Male	0.31	Significant	Low	Accepted
	Female	0.44	Significant	Moderate	Accepted
Region	Urban	0.39	Significant	Low	Accepted
	Rural	0.41	Significant	Moderate	Accepted
College Type	Govt	-0.23	Significant	-ve Low	Accepted
	Aided	0.29	Significant	Low	Accepted
	Unaided	0.44	Significant	Moderate	Accepted
Age	Upto 40yrs	0.43	Significant	Moderate	Accepted
	Above 40 yrs	0.35	Significant	Low	Accepted
Experience	Upto 10 yrs	0.44	Significant	Moderate	Accepted
	Above 10 yrs	0.31	Significant	Low	Accepted
Total Correlation(2-tailed)		0.40	Significant	Low	Accepted

Interpretation:-

The above table shows that the null hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusion:-

There is a significant Correlation between Organizational Climate of colleges of Education and Attitude of Teacher-Educators towards teaching profession.

The Correlation is significant at 0.05 level on the basis of Gender, Region, Type of College, Age & Teaching experience. In case of Type of college it can be observed that there is a positive significant Correlation between Organizational Climate of Aided and unaided colleges of Education and Attitude of Teacher-Educators towards teaching profession but there is negative and significant Correlation between Organizational Climate of Government colleges of Education and Attitude of Teacher-Educators towards teaching profession

CONCLUSIONS

On doing the analysis it has been found that -----

Organizational Climate as perceived by Teacher- Educators according to gender, according to age groups, and with varied years of teaching experience does not differ significantly but it differs as per the type of college i.e. Govt., Aided and Unaided colleges of Education. The study indicated that Organizational Climate of Aided colleges of Education is more conducive as compared to that of Govt. and Unaided colleges of Education. It also differs in terms of Organizational Structure according to region of the college i.e. urban or rural

On the basis of Correlation it can be concluded that---

Correlation between Organizational Climate and Attitude Scale towards teaching profession. as showed by this study prove that if the Organizational Climate is favourable, teacher educators attribute higher attitude towards teaching profession.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

According to the researcher, this study would be significant in the following ways:
The topic under investigation is the one that is concerned not only with teacher-educators but also with the managing authorities of the colleges of education. Hence it would make a contribution to the field of education. The findings of the study would enable teacher-educators to analyze themselves

The findings of the study would also enable the college administrators to examine the existing organizational climate & find out how it can be further enriched

This study would also be helpful to educational planners as it would suggest them the ideal organizational climate. The planners can make sufficient changes in the existing climate.

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